

The Effect of Organic and Inorganic Fertilizers on Soil Fertility and Crop Production - A Review

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Abstract

Now a days, with the present rate of population growth and the scarcity of food, it is imperative to boost soil fertility and agricultural output. For crop plants to sustain their normal physiological processes, they need nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium. Fertilizers include all the components needed to grow plants while enhancing the soil's chemical, physical, and biological qualities. The organic fertilizers were highly effective, cost-effective, and easy to carry around in large quantities. Similarly, inorganic fertilizers were known for their high cost and negative environmental impact if improperly managed. The impacts of both organic and inorganic fertilizers on crop productivity and soil fertility were reviewed in the current study. Combining organic and inorganic fertilizers builds soil health, increases the effectiveness of recommended inorganic fertilizer use, and minimizes the cost of the latter type of fertilizer. Continuous research and field trials are necessary to refine our understanding and practices, ensuring the development of effective, environmentally friendly, and economically viable fertilization strategies for sustainable agriculture.

Keywords: Organic, inorganic, soil fertility, crop production and balanced application

Introduction:

Now a days, with the present rate of population growth and the scarcity of food, it is imperative to boost soil fertility and agricultural output. One of the primary issues in crop production is less soil fertility (Javed *et al.*, 2022). Using both organic and inorganic fertilizers can increase soil fertility; however, using inorganic fertilizers in excessive amounts might decrease soil fertility.

The organic fertilizers were highly effective, cost-effective, and easy to carry around in large quantities. Similarly, inorganic fertilizers were known for their high cost and negative environmental impact if improperly managed. According to Assefa and Tadesse (2019), the use of inorganic fertilizers is advantageous in a shorter amount of time but has more adverse effects, such as soil compaction, erosion, and decreased soil fertility. Enhancing soil fertility and agricultural yield can be achieved by several methods, such as applying fertilizers and beneficial bacteria. The microbial population in soil functions as a bioindicator of crop productivity, soil biome, sustainability, and sensitive pointer of soil quality.

Combining organic and inorganic fertilizers builds soil health, increases the effectiveness of recommended inorganic fertilizer use, and minimizes the cost of the latter type of fertilizer (Roba, 2018; Verma *et al.*, 2020). It also has a greater positive impact on microbial biomass. According to Kugbe *et al.*, (2019), the idea of soil fertility is based on physical, chemical, and biological characteristics and will increase crop productivity. The impacts of both organic and inorganic fertilizers on crop productivity and soil fertility were reviewed in the current study.

Importance of Fertilizers:

Fertilizers are substances that include one or more nutrient components in the form of both organic and inorganic chemical molecules. For crop plants to sustain their normal physiological processes, they need nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium (Wang *et al.*, 2021). These micronutrients are intended to meet the plants lesser but still essential needs, which is why these fertilizers are designed to supply tiny amounts of nutrients. These macronutrients are extremely important for the healthy and non-restrictive growth of any plant, and they also significantly increase yields (Hazra, 2016). Fertilizers include all the components needed to grow plants while enhancing the soil's chemical, physical, and biological qualities (Sharma and Chetani, 2017).

Organic Fertilizers:

According to Assefa and Tadesse (2019), organic fertilizers are substances with a specific chemical composition and high analytical value that provide plant nutrients in an accessible form. Organic fertilizers are natural materials of either plant or animal source, including livestock manure, green manures, crop residues, household waste, compost, and works directly as a source of plant nutrients and indirectly influences the physical, chemical and biological properties of soil (Bhatt *et al.*, 2019).

Applying organic fertilizers will increase the soil's organic matter, soil water retention, soil nitrogen content, nutrient mobilization, and enhanced nutrient availability. They will also shield the soil from wind and rain erosion and release nutrients more gradually. A significant amount of organic fertilizer must be applied because improperly processed organic fertilizers contain pathogens that are harmful to humans and plants. Additionally, because the composition of organic fertilizers is highly variable, it is challenging to apply nutrients accurately to match plant production (Roba, 2018).

Inorganic Fertilizers:

Inorganic agricultural fertilizers are defined as those that are made up of inorganic chemical compounds. Most of these fertilizers do not biodegrade. Because they are produced in factories utilizing modern technologies, these fertilizers are sometimes known as artificial or synthetic fertilizers (Hazra, 2016).

When inorganic fertilizer is applied in a balanced manner, it can increase soil organic matter, boost crop yield, and improve soil fertility. Since these nutrients are already soluble in water, the effects are often immediate and the plant grows quickly because it has all the nutrients it needs. Little amounts of inorganic fertilizers are needed for productivity because they have a high nutrient content (Bhatt *et al.*, 2019).

Overuse of chemical fertilizers can alter soil quality parameters, diminishing the amount of organic matter and humus in the soil, slowing plant development, frustrating beneficial organisms, changing the PH value of the soil, increasing pests, and increasing greenhouse gas emissions. According to Ilahi *et al.*, (2020), using inorganic fertilizers exclusively can be hazardous and over time can contaminate the soil.

Effect of organic and inorganic fertilizers on soil fertility:

A key factor that influences crop plant yield, nutritional value, and capacity for reproductive growth is soil fertility. According to Bodruzzaman *et al.*, (2010), there was a substantial response in the soil's pH, % OM, %total N, accessible P, exchangeable K, and available S content when organic and inorganic fertilizers were applied. The buildup of organic carbon in soils under a rice–rice cropping system was 40, 60, and 58 kg t⁻¹ of rice straw, cow dung, and poultry manure, respectively, during five rice-growing seasons, according to research by Rahman *et al.*, (2016). This could vary depending on the initial carbon contents of residues applied to soil.

It has been demonstrated that chemical fertilizers directly and efficiently increase soil fertility in low-fertility fields. On the other hand, the N in organic fertilizers breaks down more slowly and is more readily held in the soil, while the inorganic N in chemical fertilizers breaks down quickly and is easily lost (Ma *et al.*, 2023). Thus, in areas with differing fertility levels, combining organic and inorganic fertilization is a long-term successful approach.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the impact of organic and inorganic fertilizers on soil fertility and crop production is a complex interplay of various factors. While both types of fertilizers contribute essential nutrients to the soil, organic fertilizers promote long-term soil health, microbial activity, and sustainability. They also enhance soil structure and water retention. On the other hand, inorganic fertilizers provide readily available nutrients and can lead to higher short-term crop yields.

Effect of organic and inorganic fertilizers on crop production:

S. No	Crop	Type of fertilizer	Result	Place of research	Reference
1.	Rice	Both Organic and Inorganic	The results revealed that the application of enriched poultry manure compost on equal N basis (2.3 t ha ⁻¹) recorded higher growth parameters, yield attributes and grain yield of 4953 kg ha ⁻¹ .	Ethiopia	Redda and Abay (2015)
2.	Wheat	Both Organic and Inorganic	It found that the Treatment T ₉ (100% NPK + 5 t ha ⁻¹ FYM + 5t ha ⁻¹ vermicompost + PSB), was found best in the terms of plant population, growth parameters, grain yield, straw yield, harvest index and B:C ratio.	Kanpur, India	Kumar and Niwas (2022)
3.	Maize	Both Organic and Inorganic	The combined application of FYM, vermicompost and chemical fertilizers (50% Recommended dose of NPK + 25% FYM + 25% Vermicompost) gives significantly higher results in growth parameters and yield attributes as well as yield as compared to rest of treatments as well as control.	Punjab, India	Singh and Misal (2022)
4.	Sorghum	Organic	The highest rate of Sorghum physiological growth indexes root and net assimilation rate were belonged to the co-inoculation of mycorrhiza + Nitroxin treatment (T ₂).	Iran	Kamaei <i>et al.</i> , (2019)
5.	Pearl millet	Both Organic and Inorganic	The significantly higher grain yield (3.18 t/ha), stover yield (6.39 t/ha) and harvest index (33.22%) were recorded with the application of 75% RDN with 50% Poultry manure compared to all other treatments.	Uttar Pradesh, India	Amarghade and Singh (2021)
6.	Groundnut	Organic	The results of this investigation revealed that the application of 50 % N (FYM) + 25 % N (Vermicompost) + Rhizobium + PSB (Seed treatment) (T ₃) had significant effect on haulm yield of groundnut (4622 kg ha ⁻¹).	Gujarat, India	Kulkarni <i>et al.</i> , (2018)
7.	Sunflower	Both Organic and Inorganic	The Result indicated that the treatment 100 % RDF + FYM @ 5 t/ha (T ₂) recorded significantly higher growth & yield attributes.	Maharashtra, India	Dambale <i>et al.</i> , (2017)
8.	Mung bean	Both Organic and Inorganic	it can be concluded that 50% vermicompost mixed with 50% recommended fertilizers showed excellent results in growth and yield parameters.	Pakistan	Aslam <i>et al.</i> , (2024)
9.	Barely	Both Organic and Inorganic	The combined application of vermicompost @ 4.5 t ha ⁻¹ + 40kg N gave higher grain yield (5.59 t ha ⁻¹) and straw yield (7.06 t ha ⁻¹) over rest of other combinations of organic manure and nitrogen.	Rajasthan, India	Kumawat <i>et al.</i> , (2006)

A balanced and integrated approach, combining the strengths of both organic and inorganic fertilizers, tailored to specific soil and crop needs, appears to be a promising strategy. It is crucial to consider environmental sustainability and the long-term health of the soil, striving for a harmonious coexistence of agricultural productivity and ecological balance. Continuous research and field trials are necessary to refine our understanding and practices, ensuring the development of effective, environmentally friendly, and economically viable fertilization strategies for sustainable agriculture.

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